

Benzimidazoles. Part IV. Synthesis of 2-(*m*-Nitro- α -hydroxybenzyl)benzimidazoles

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Some substituted 2-(*m*-nitro- α -hydroxybenzyl)benzimidazoles have been synthesised by condensing suitably substituted aromatic *o*-diamines with *m*-nitromandelic acid. The condensation takes place smoothly in presence of 6 *N*-HCl, providing as high as 95% yields in some cases. Various substituents have been placed at 4(7)-5(6)-5, 6, or 4,6(5,7), position of the benzo moiety, a methyl group at N¹ of the imidazole function, and a nitro group at the *m*-position of the phenyl moiety of the hydroxybenzyl part.

Since the demonstration of the virus-inhibitory activity and selectivity of a variety of benzimidazole derivatives¹, there has been keen interest in the synthesis of other substituted 2-(α -hydroxybenzyl)benzimidazoles (HBB) in search for enhanced activity and minimised toxicity. Quite a large number of HBB analogues with a variety of substituents have been synthesised recently by Folkers and co-workers² and in our laboratory.³ We now report the synthesis of various analogues of HBB with a nitro group at the *m*-position of the phenyl moiety of the hydroxybenzyl part and other substituents, like chloro, bromo, nitro, methoxy, and methyl groups, on the benzo moiety, and a methyl group at N¹ of the imidazole function. The various substituents introduced may affect the pharmacology of the hydroxybenzylbenzimidazoles.

All the analogues of HBB were synthesised by condensing a suitably substituted aromatic *o*-diamine with *m*-nitromandelic acid under acidic media. The methods⁴⁻⁵ employed for the synthesis of simple and substituted benzimidazoles were attempted, but under those conditions the condensation of 1:1.5 molar proportions of substituted aromatic *o*-diamines with *m*-nitromandelic acid resulted in low yields. 6 *N*-HCl was subsequently found to be very effective medium which promoted smooth intermolecular condensation between the *ortho*-diamine and the acid with as high yield as 80-99%. Usually a reaction period of 7-10 hr. at 120-30° was required for a facile condensation. The benzimidazole separated as the monohydrochloride from the reaction mixture was converted quantitatively to the free base by careful addition of sodium carbonate. The various hydroxybenzylbenzimidazoles, thus synthesised, are described in Table I.

1. Tamm *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1953, 47, 11827; 1954, 48, 13077; 1961, 55, 18687.
2. Wagner *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 3236.
3. Revankar *et al.*, *J. Karnatak Univ.*, 1964, 9, 67; *Monatsh.*, in press; *J. Karnatak Univ.*, in press.
4. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2393.
5. Shriner and Upson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 2277.

EXPERIMENTAL

The first group of intermediates, viz., suitably substituted aromatic *o*-diamines, like 3-chloro-⁶, 4, 6-dichloro-⁷, 4,5-dichloro-⁸, 3-bromo-^{6c}, 4,6-dibromo-⁹, *N*-methyl-¹⁰, 4,5-dimethyl-¹¹, 4-nitro-¹² and 4-methoxy-*o*-phenylenediamino¹³, were obtained by known methods. The other intermediate, viz., *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, was prepared from benzaldehyde. Benzaldehyde was nitrated at 0-5° to provide *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde¹⁴ which on treatment with potassium cyanide and glacial acetic acid afforded the cyanohydrin¹⁵. The cyanohydrin was immediately hydrolysed with HCl(conc.) to obtain *m*-nitrobenzoic acid¹⁵.

TABLE I

2-(*m*-Nitro- α -hydroxybenzyl)benzimidazoles.

S. No.	Substituents.					Yield.	M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
	R ₁ .	R ₂ .	R ₃ .	R ₄ .	R ₅ .				Found.	Reqd.
1*	H	H	H	H	H	..	200-201°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃	15.52	15.61
2	Monohydrochloride of 1					09%	235°	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ .HCl	13.62	13.75
3	H	Cl	H	H	H	..	164-05°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.02	13.84
4	Monohydrochloride of 3					58	228°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ .Cl.HCl	12.03	12.35
5	H	H	Cl	H	Cl	..	182°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂	12.59	12.43
6	Monohydrochloride of 5					99	222-23°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ .HCl	10.92	11.21
7	H	H	Cl	Cl	H	56	222°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Cl ₂ .HCl	11.07	11.21
8	H	Br	H	H	H	..	163-64°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Br	11.93	12.07
9	Monohydrochloride of 8					50	233-34°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ Br.HCl	11.08	10.92
10	H	H	Br	H	Br	..	186-87°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₂	10.23	9.84
11	Monohydrochloride of 10					84	238-37°	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Br ₂ .HCl	9.48	9.06
12	Me	H	H	H	H	..	161°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	14.66	14.84
13	Monohydrochloride of 12					00	235°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ .HCl	12.90	13.14
14	H	H	Me	Me	H	..	250°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	14.38	14.14
15	Monohydrochloride of 14					54	263-66°	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃ .HCl	12.24	12.60
16	H	H	NO ₂	H	H	88	243-44°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ .HCl	16.29	15.98
17	H	H	OMe	H	H	..	195-97°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃	13.97	14.05
18	Monohydrochloride of 17					50	220°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ .HCl	12.08	12.52

*Wagner *et al.*². obtained in 39% yield.

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General Procedure for the Preparation of 2-(m-Nitro- α -hydroxybenzyl)-benzimidazoles.—A solution of an appropriately substituted aromatic *o*-diamine (0.01 *M*) and *m*-nitromandelic acid (0.015 *M*) in 6 *N*-HCl (20 ml) was heated under reflux at 130° for 7-8 hr. and allowed to stand overnight. The reaction mixture was ice-cooled; the crude monohydrochloride of 2-(*m*-nitro- α -hydroxybenzyl)benzimidazole precipitating from the acid solution was collected, washed thoroughly with anhydrous ether, and dried. All the hydrochlorides were crystallised from a mixture of dry ethanol-ether with the aid of decolorising carbon as well-defined crystalline needles.

The above monohydrochlorides were quantitatively converted to the free bases by dissolving them in minimum amount of water and adding the calculated quantity of sodium carbonate. The free bases, thus obtained, were collected, washed well with cold water, and crystallised usually from aqueous ethanol to furnish analytically pure samples.

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